

THE LENGTH OF THE WOOL FIBER IN LAMBS SUR KARAKALPAK BREED TYPE

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Annotation. The article presents the results of a study on the severity of the length of the wool fiber and the degree of grayness in offspring obtained from homogeneous and heterogeneous mating of Karakul sheep of the Karakalpak breed type.

Keywords: soreness level, manifestation (contrast), colorfulness, wool fiber, homogen mating, heterogen mating, colorability.

Introduction. During the years of independence in our republic, extensive measures were taken to improve its breeding by organizing the selection of cattle breeds in surin scabies, the length of wool fibers, especially in sur sheeps, is a factor that directly affects the brand indicators of the skin and is associated with the appearance of its curls. The length of the wool fiber determines the degree of soreness to a certain extent. The greater the soreness level, depending on the length of the wool fibers of the skin, leads to a decrease in the quality indicators of the skin, as well as an increase in the skin coverage of the white color.

In the research of many scientists note that the transition from black to white in wool fibers confirms that the best image level will be moist, the skin grade will be higher if the part is 3/10 or 4/10. The length and shape of the wool

fiber is one of the indicators that determines the main pronounced properties of the skin in the field of scabies. The fact that the wool fiber is excessively long or thick also has a negative effect on the quality of the scab. The reason is that the wool fibers are long, which leads to the loosening of the flowers on the skin, and the large one, so that they can not take the form of the necessary amount of curls. This track will in turn cause low quality skins to appear. Therefore, it is important to take into account the length of the wool fiber. Such thoughts are expressed by many scientists, noted that one of the reasons for the poor quality of the skin in relation to the Black color of the calves and lambs of color is the length of their fibers. In the conclusion of scientists, the length of the fiber in the coloring of wool fibers and changes depending on the intensity of its color, the idea that black fibers will be shorter, if light colors, then longer.

Purpose of the study. It consists of studying the properties of wool (wool length and degree of pigmentation) of lambs, obtained from homogeneous (homogeneous) and heterogeneous (heterogeneous) selection of colors and developing ways to increase the number of animals with the desired productive qualities of karakul sheep of the karakalpak breed type.

Research objective. It consists of studying the properties of wool in lambs obtained from homogeneous and heterogeneous selection of karakul sheep of the Karakalpak breed type according to the colors.

The object of the study is the offspring of karakul sheep sur of the Karakalpak breed type obtained from homogeneous and heterogeneous selection of parents according to colors.

Research methods. The quality indicators of the offspring, obtained during the research, were assessed on the basis of the “Guide to breeding work and evaluation (grading) of lambs” (Yusupov S.Yu. and dr., 2015). The obtained data were processed by methods of variation statistics according to the textbook “Guide to Biometrics for Livestock Scientists” (N.A. Plokhinsky, 1969).

Results of the experiment. Results of our experimental work the data obtained on the length of wool fibers in sur skins and the degree of soreness are presented in Table 1.

Length of wool fiber in lambs (in the rump),

in millimeters

Types of mating	Number of lambs (head)	Jaket type	Rib type	Flat type	Caucasian type
$X \pm S_x$					
ShGxPS	73	11,2 $\pm$ 0,07	12,2 $\pm$ 0,6	10,6 $\pm$ 0,21	14,0 $\pm$ 0,40
UGxPS	81	12,3 $\pm$ 0,07	12,1 $\pm$ 0,41	10,7 $\pm$ 0,13	13,3 $\pm$ 0,28
PSxPS	57	11,9 $\pm$ 0,07	12,2 $\pm$ 0,35	10,3 $\pm$ 0,25	12,6 $\pm$ 0,42
QSxPS	54	12,4 $\pm$ 0,10	12,8 $\pm$ 0,22	11,5 $\pm$ 0,19	14,2 $\pm$ 0,09

The results of Table 1 data analysis showed that the measurement of the length of the wool fiber showed that while it was the length of the thickest wool fiber (10,6 $\pm$ 0,21) in the Spruce obtained from the flat-type spruce x steel horn, UGxPS, PSxPS and QSxPS pairing. respectively, was equal to 10,7 $\pm$ 0,13; 10,3 $\pm$ 0,25 and 11,5 $\pm$ 0,19. That is, in generations from QSxPS 14,2 $\pm$ 0,09 mm, if this indicator is considered to be 100%, then it was observed that PSxPS is 1,6%, in generations from UGxPS 0,9 mm and ShGxPS generations wool fiber length 0,2% are shorter. It can be concluded that the length of wool fibers is associated with skin types, and the more flat-type barra skins, the shorter the wool fibers in the same group were considered. The average length of wool fibers in generations derived from homogen and geterogen pairing is shown in aigure 1 in the figure

below.

1-picture. The length of wool fibers in generations derived from different pairing

The analysis of the data in Figure 1 shows that the steel wool was found to be the longest wool fiber in the generations obtained from the mating of rams with sheep. This suggests that the number of generations belonging to the Caucasian type among the lambs of the lunar flower variety is explained by the large number and length of wool fibers

The degree of tanning of black leather is the main indicator of the brightness of the skin, the appearance of quality indicators, and depends on the color and variety. Such views are confirmed by the fact that the level of surk depends on the color of the sur sheep belonging to the Surkhandarya type.

The hereditary characteristics of these two traits were observed in the homogeneous pairing of Bukhara sur sheep. Similar changes were observed in Surkhandarya Sur Karakol sheep and Karakalpak Pulati Sur sheep.

The data on the level of wool fiber content of Karakalpak sheep are given in Table 2. Karakalpak Sur provides the elegance of the skin with the surly level of the wool fiber of the lambs, i.e. the border from the black section to the flow section. This elegance is mainly obtained from the brightest and most attractive skins with a skin tone level of 3/10 and 4/10.

Table 2. The degree of color intensity in Karakalpak lambs sur

Types of mating	Number of lambs (head)	Average length of wool fiber, mm	Photo level				
			1/10	2/10	3/10	4/10	5/10
			X±Sx				
ShG xPS	73	12,0	1,4±1, 37	12,3±3, 84	27,4±5, 22	45,2±5, 82	13,7±4, 02
UGx PS	81	12,1	2,5±1, 73	8,6±3,1 2	32,0±5, 18	42,0±5, 48	14,8±3, 95
PSx PS	57	11,75	1,7±1, 71	5,3±2,9 6	31,6±6, 15	49,1±6, 62	12,3±4, 35
QSx PS	54	12,73	3,7±2, 56	7,4±3,5 6	22,2±5, 65	37,0±6, 57	29,7±6, 21

According to this indicator, the ShGxPS generation was 72,6%, the UGxPS generation was 74,0%, the PSxPS mating generation was 80,7%, and the QSxPS generation was 59,2%. The highest scores on 3/10 and 4/10 shear rates were

recorded in steel shear lambs obtained from 80,7% homogeneous pairing. Comparing the differences between the colors, the QSxPS paired offspring decreased by 21,5%, the UGxPS paired offspring decreased by 6,7% and the ShGxPS offspring decreased by 8,1% was found to be

Conclusion. Based on the research, it can be concluded that in the skins of steel sur color, the fineness of the skin increases at the level of 3/10 and 4/10 surl when the curl is not fully wrapped, forming a semicircle.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Yusupov S.Yu. Improving the gene pool of the Karakol sheep breed on a scientific basis. «Problems of ecologically balanced use of the gene pool of desert and pasture livestock.» Scientific collection. Samarkand. 2010, page. 9-12.

2. Gigieneyshvili N.S. Uspexi I zadachi svetnogo karakulevodstva. Karakulevodstvo. Vip XI.T.1980. page 35-36.

3. Axmetshiev A.S. Seleksiya karakulskix ovets karakalpaskogo sura. Almarata. It's hot. 1989. page 33-34.

4. Ismailov M.Sh., Gaziev A.G., Fazilov U.T., Ibragimov J.X. Osobennosti rosta karakulskix yagnyat v razlichnix ekologicheskix zonax v zavisimosti ot tipa rozhdeniya. Collection of materials 1 International scientific practical internet conference «Modern ecological conditions of natural environment and scientific practical aspects of rational use» S. Solyonoe zaimishche. Astrakhan. Russia. 2016. page 181.

5. Gaziev A and dr. Seleksionno-geneticheskie i ekologicheskie aspekti effektivnogo ispolzovaniya produktivnogo potentsiala chernix karakulskix ovets, V. ab. Rabot «Problems of development of desert-pastoral cattle breeding». Samarkand 2005. page 52-59.

6. Xatamov A. X. Wool-fiber quality indicators of Karakalpak Sur Karakul

lambs in the new ecological conditions. Proceedings of the international scientific-practical conference «Scientific and practical basis for the development of desert pasture and prevention of desertification.» Samarkand, 2019, page 51-53.